

Reflexives in German Learner Language

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This documents contains the appendices to the paper “Reflexives in German Learner Language” by AUTHORS.

A Determining Functional Types

The functional type dimension addresses two questions. First, do the referents of the subject and the object fill the roles of agent and patient simultaneously, by performing the action denoted by the verb on each other, as in Example (1)? If that is the case, the functional type of the construction is *reciprocal*.

- (1) *Maja und Ben begrüßen sich.*
Maja and Ben greet REFL
'Maja and Ben greet each.other.'

If the answer to the first question is no, namely, we do not identify a reciprocal function, we go on to ask the second question: does the trigger allow for the reflexive pronoun to take an argument role? One way to test this is to substitute the reflexive pronoun with a full noun phrase (NP) (Helbig and Buscha 2001, p. 188, Kunze 1997, p. 89-90). If this is possible without the trigger or antecedent changing their meaning, it means that the reflexive marker has a genuine contribution, and we therefore label this *semantic reflexivity*. In the most straightforward case, the reflexive does take an argument role, patient, while the antecedent (in most cases: The subject of the phrase) takes the role of agent, as in Example (2).

- (2) *Peter rasiert sich.*
Peter rasiert REFL
'Peter shaves.'

The reason the patient position is marked with a reflexive and not a mere oblique case on some other NP is that its referent coincides with the antecedent's referent: The shaver is also the one shaved. If the reflexive were substituted by a full NP, the verb *shave* would retain its meaning, as in Example (3).

- (3) *Peter rasiert den Vater.*
Peter shaves the.ACC father
'Peter shaves the father.'

29 In cases where the antecedent and the reflexive only syntactically refer to the same referent, but
30 no argument role seems to be reserved for the reflexive pronoun, as in Example (4), *sich* cannot
31 be replaced with a full NP. Here, there is one person taking care of the grandmother (*Peter*, the
32 antecedent) and there is a slot of an accusative object filled by the reflexive pronoun (not, as might
33 be expected, the patient, who appears in a prepositional phrase). The accusative slot does not match
34 with the patient role, nor any additional role, so *sich* is semantically empty, but it must formally
35 agree with the subject. As the semantic contribution of the reflexive pronoun is not transparent,
36 and since the verb cannot appear without its reflexive pronoun, we call such constructions *lexical*
37 *reflexives*.

38 (4) *Peter kümmert sich um seine Großmutter.*
Peter takes-care REFL of his grandmother
39 ‘Peter takes care of his grandmother.’

40 Finally, another case of an apparent role mismatch is shown in Example (??), repeated here as
41 Example (5). As *öffnen* only allots one argument role, it should not have an accusative object, but
42 the accusative slot is nevertheless instantiated by the reflexive pronoun, which must agree with its
43 antecedent, here *Tür*. It cannot be replaced with a full NP, either.¹ These forms only appear in the
44 third person with inanimate subjects, and despite the formal agreement between the antecedent and
45 the reflexive pronoun, no function of coreferentiality can in any way be assumed. Instead there is
46 always a de-agentivized, non-volitional action. The functional type of this construction is therefore
47 *middle*.

48 (5) *Die Tür öffnet sich.*
the door opens REFL
49 ‘The door opens.’

50 B Examples of the Annotation Scheme

51 In Example (2), *Peter rasiert sich* ‘Peter shaves’, the trigger *rasiert* is assigned with the tags [SEM]
52 [ACC] [PRES]. This is the most unmarked configuration possible: In the trigger verb *rasieren*, the
53 agent and the patient are truly coreferential. Both the antecedent (*Peter*) and the reflexive pronoun
54 are arguments of the same predicate, and the reflexive pronoun is present (which is not always the
55 case in learner texts).

56 In Example (4), *Peter kümmert sich um seine Großmutter* ‘Peter takes care of his grandmother’,
57 the trigger is the verb *kümmern*. The values of CASE, and the presence of reflexive PRONOUN are
58 the same as above: [ACC] and [PRES]. But the feature FUNCTIONAL TYPE takes the value [LEX]
59 because *sich* does not match with any argument role; it cannot be replaced by another NP without
60 the trigger losing its meaning.

61 In Example (5), *Die Tür öffnet sich* ‘The door opens’, the trigger is the verb *öffnen*. Again,
62 it matches Example (4) in the feature CASE and the presence of reflexive PRONOUN. The feature

¹A more transformational account would be: *öffnen* as a transitive verb is de-transitivized by the occupation of its object slot through the reflexive pronoun. *Sich* thus acts like a semantically empty place holder, and, therefore, as a marker of detransitivization. This is a rough simplification of approaches that treat reflexives as part of voice. [Geniušienė \(1987, p. 8-18\)](#) presents this strand of research as juxtaposed to treating reflexives as derivation. A more recent representation can be found in [Alexiadou \(2014\)](#).

63 FUNCTIONAL TYPE is assigned the value [MIDDLE] because the subject *Tür* ‘door’ is inanimate
64 and non-agentive. The complete complex tag is thus [MIDDLE] [ACC] [PRES].

65 (6) *Anna und Paul freunden sich an* .
Anna and Paul become.friends REFL PTCL
66 ‘Anna and Paul become friends.’

67 Example (6), *Anna und Paul freunden sich an* ‘Anna and Paul become friends’, is associated
68 with the following tags on *anfreunden*: [REC] [ACC] [PRES]. Since the trigger verb is unambigu-
69 ously reciprocal it receives the tag [REC].

70 These four instances are exemplary of the most common types of reflexive use in German.

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